

Methodological and Ideological Options

Reconceptualizing the role of socioeconomic material stocks in the leverage points framework to enable transformative change

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ABSTRACT

Addressing the intensifying climate crisis and the transgression of multiple Planetary Boundaries requires a deep socio-ecological transformation. From the perspective of complex systems, the following question arises: Which leverage points need to be addressed to push socio-economic systems in a more sustainable direction? While we agree that the leverage points heuristic proposed by Donella Meadows is useful, we herein argue that it would benefit from emphasizing the pivotal role of socioeconomic material stocks as enablers and inhibitors of transformative change. Currently, socioeconomic stocks are pigeonholed as a shallow leverage point. However, from a socio-metabolic perspective, existing stocks are key drivers of environmental pressures, which foster unsustainable individual behaviours and thus create path dependencies and lock-ins. Stocks can even shape the societal perception of challenges that often foster unsustainable responses. Hence, system-wide socio-ecological change hinges on fundamental changes in socioeconomic stocks. Transformative change requires a reconceptualization of stocks embracing their multidimensional and cross-cutting interconnectedness with the deeper leverage points around system feedback, design, and intent. Rather than looking for the one deep leverage point, we suggest that a well-coordinated intervention strategy needs to target multiple leverage points while systematically considering socioeconomic stocks as an inherent, critical system property to be altered.

1. Introduction

Multiple global sustainability crises require transformative, urgent, and targeted societal responses. However, current interventions tend to focus on short-term, pragmatic approaches that fail to address the root causes of unsustainability (Dorninger et al., 2020; Fischer et al., 2007). While appreciation of the complexity of sustainability problems is on the rise, understanding of where and how to intervene into socioeconomic systems is lacking. One approach to address the ‘where and how’ of transformative change is Donella Meadows’ leverage points (Meadows, 1997, 1999a, 1999b) framework. It provides a heuristic model for systematizing system transformation processes by describing leverage points as those places of a complex system “where a small shift in one thing can produce big changes in everything” (Meadows, 1999a, p. 1). Another later description of her states that a leverage point is “a place in the system where a small change could lead to a large shift in [system] behaviour” (Meadows, 2009, p. 145). The originally proposed leverage

points framework describes twelve leverage points in increasing order of effectiveness (from, 12–1, see Fig. 1). They are ranging from changing system parameters, buffers and stocks (easiest to change, but least effective) to addressing system feedbacks, goals and paradigms (with the greatest potential for effecting transformative change).

A growing number of scholars has taken up the leverage points concept of Meadows (1999a), as well as its further development by Abson et al. (2017). The concept was used in multiple ways: (1) Interventions and sustainability transformation in socioeconomic systems were discussed regarding their potential effectiveness (Fischer and Riechers, 2019; Haas et al., 2023; Mandl, 2023; Riechers et al., 2022; Rosengren et al., 2020). (2) Proposed or implemented interventions were assessed from a systemic perspective (Angheloiu and Tennant, 2020; Dorninger et al., 2020; Zimmermann et al., 2023). (3) It was also further developed for other but similar purposes (Chan et al., 2020; Gladkykh et al., 2018; Sahin et al., 2020). Thus, the leverage points framework provides a common approach for conceptualizing both

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transformative change itself, and the characteristics of the systems in which such transformations occur (Leventon et al., 2021).

So far, the leverage points approach has no systemic biophysical conceptualization of socioeconomic systems in which one might want to intervene. We argue that interventions into complex socioeconomic systems should be based also on a comprehensive understanding of their social metabolism of materials, energy, waste and emissions, and the material stocks of buildings, infrastructure and machinery. Socio-metabolic research aims at systematically understanding the biophysical basis of society by investigating how resource use interlinks with the use and reproduction of socioeconomic material stocks, which results in waste and emissions (Haberl, 2006; Haberl et al., 2019). The scale and composition of social metabolism is directly related to two aspects: Firstly, to the socioeconomic material stocks¹ of buildings, infrastructure, machinery and other short-lived goods utilized and reproduced by a given socioeconomic system. Secondly, to the environmental impact societies exert on the natural world (Krausmann et al., 2017b; Pauliuk and Müller, 2014; United Nations Environment Programme, and International Resource Panel, 2024). Socioeconomic material stocks play

crucial roles in unsustainable path development, e.g. through the large volumes of resources to build and maintain them as well as the lock-ins into specific resource use patterns (Krausmann et al., 2020). From this perspective, we argue that more emphasis needs to be placed on how material stocks are conceptualized in ongoing academic work using the framework the leverage points to better understand potentials for transformative change.

In the following, we discuss the importance of material stocks for transformative change from a leverage points perspective vis-à-vis a social metabolic perspective. In this way, we aim to identify crucial insights and differences which support our argument for a reconceptualization of the role of material stocks in the leverage points framework. We discuss this new understanding of stocks as cross-cutting and multi-dimensional leverage points for transformative change in the leverage points heuristic. We further unveil the interconnectedness of material stocks with deeper leverage points around system feedback, design, and intent to enable transformative change. Illustrative examples provide direction on how the further benefits of the leverage point heuristic can be enhanced.

Fig. 1. The upper part shows the leverage points scale on a lever adapted from Meadows (1999a) and four summarizing system characteristics by Abson et al. (2017). The twelve leverage points are ranked from left to right and portrayed to act on a lever with the far-right one having the highest impact. The red parts of the leverage points description indicate strong and direct connections with socioeconomic-material stocks as suggested by Meadows. Directed red arrows relate the leverage points which directly address socioeconomic material stocks, following Meadows (1999a). The part below the lever shows the socioeconomic material stocks as part of a socioeconomic system and require material and energy inputs (inflows). Waste flows and emissions (to air, water, or land) from material stocks leave the socioeconomic system as outflows and enter the natural environment, causing adverse impacts like climate change or environmental pollution and hazard, thereby causing the overstepping of several planetary boundaries. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

¹ Socioeconomic stocks, as we define them, are sometimes also referred to as ‘in-use stocks’ and are a subset of fixed assets as defined in the European Standard Accounts (OECD, 2008, p. 206). They include the built environment (infrastructure and buildings) and artefacts (machinery and consumer durables) (Fischer-Kowalski, 2011; Fischer-Kowalski et al., 2011). Together with humans, livestock and other domestic animals, the socioeconomic stocks form the totality of stocks in social metabolism (Pauliuk and Müller, 2014).

2. The role of stocks in the leverage points vis-à-vis the social metabolic perspective

The leverage point concept (re)gained attention in the scientific community following a contribution of Abson et al. (2017), who proposed a new research agenda for socioeconomic systems and sustainability transformation inspired by Meadows’ (1997, 1999a) seminal leverage points framework. The authors group Meadows’ original

twelve leverage points into ‘shallow’ (12–7) and ‘deep’ (6–1) leverage points. In so doing, they followed Meadows’ proposed order of effectiveness, where effectiveness can be thought of as transformative power, where shallow leverage points are considered less effective in initiating a long-lasting transformative change. The ‘shallow’ leverage points can be seen as being more frequently used by policy/decision makers (Dorninger et al., 2020), because it is more obvious how to envision and address them. But at the same time, it has been argued that they rarely address the root cause of problems. In contrast, interventions into deep leverage points – envisioned as being more effective for change— are believed to address the root causes of unsustainability. Abson et al. (2017) further classified the twelve leverage points in groups of three, which represent four broader system components. The four system characteristics are parameters, feedback, design, and intent, which are also understood in a nested hierarchy (Abson et al., 2017; Riechers et al., 2022). Thereby, changes to parameters and feedbacks are seen as relatively shallow interventions for system transformation, as they are constrained by deeper system properties. In contrast, changes to design and intent allow for deeper system change. Compare the upper part of Fig. 1 for a visualization.

The leverage points framework is embedded in system dynamics and systems thinking as practiced by Meadows. In system dynamics, stocks are elements of the system that are defined by specific characteristics through which the system’s state and behaviour can be determined. From this perspective, stocks characterize the state of the system and provide the basis for actions. Stocks provide systems with inertia and memory, but they are also the source of delays. They further decouple rates of flow and create disequilibrium dynamics (Sterman, 2000, p195ff) and they function as buffers with stabilizing effects for flows. Interventions in such stocks are considered to be relatively ineffective regarding transformative change (ranked 11th out of 12 in terms of places to intervene). Meadows (1999a, p6) states: “You hear about catastrophic river floods much more often than catastrophic lake floods, because stocks that are big, relative to their flows, are more stable than small ones”. Delays are a consequence of a system’s stock-and-flow structure and ranked as leverage point 9. As Meadows (1999a, p7) states “a delay in a feedback process is critical [...] I would list delay length as a higher leverage point except for the fact that delays are not often easily changeable”. This directly links to delays being a result of the stock-and-flow structure of a system, which Meadows directly addresses in leverage point 10. Also, the underlying physical stock-and-flow structure of a system are regarded as having limited potential to transform systems as “physical rebuilding (of stocks) is the slowest and most expensive kind of change to make in a system. Some stock-and-flow structures are just plain unchangeable” (Meadows, 1999a, p7).

Nevertheless, in systems thinking the behaviour of the system emerges from the interaction between all the system elements. Therefore, to understand where interventions might transform a system’s behaviour, it is vital to appreciate how its elements interact. However, the leverage points framework does not systemically conceptualize physical stocks within any given system, so likely feedbacks involving stocks do not yet fall within the scope of the framework. A social metabolism perspective can add to this and provide a theoretical and empirical grounding for understanding how socioeconomic material stocks shape the emergent behaviour of socioeconomic systems.

From a socio-metabolic perspective, socioeconomic material stocks are all biophysical structures existing in a defined socioeconomic (sub) system at any specific point in time, in contrast to flows that take place over a period of time. These stocks are continuously reproduced and

utilized by society (Krausmann et al., 2018). Socioeconomic material stocks include buildings, infrastructure, or machinery² which provide services to society, as well as bodies of humans and livestock (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz, 1999; Haberl et al., 2019). Socioeconomic material stocks are key determinants of the social metabolism: their production respectively construction and maintenance requires more than half of all socio-metabolic flows (Krausmann et al., 2018; Streeck et al., 2023; Wiedenhofer et al., 2021); their use during production and consumption activities furthermore locks-in energy requirements for service provisioning. Socioeconomic material stocks have also been referred to as “artefacts” (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz, 1999), “in-use stocks of materials” (Krausmann et al., 2017b; Pauliuk and Müller, 2014), technomass (Inostroza, 2014), anthropomass (Elhacham et al., 2020) and technosphere (Galbraith et al., 2024). Socio-metabolic research draws a clear distinction between natural stocks and socioeconomic material stocks. Natural stocks, for example resource deposits, are outside the boundaries of the socio-metabolic system. However, they can be utilized by society to provide flows of material and energy into socioeconomic systems, either via sustainable or unsustainable appropriation of those natural stocks by human activities. Conventions on system boundaries and distinguishing stocks inside and outside the systems of consideration have been developed over the last decades. The current consensus on system boundaries used in national-scale economy-wide material flow analysis has been established jointly between UNEP, OECD, Eurostat on the one hand (United Nations Environment Programme, 2023), and scientists on the other hand (Fischer-Kowalski et al., 2011; Krausmann et al., 2017a; Schandl et al., 2024). Thus for example, the oceans and fish, natural oil reserves, phosphor deposits in the ground, as well as forests, fields and wild land animals can be seen as natural stocks, whereas all buildings, infrastructure and products with a life-span above a year, as well as humans and livestock are considered as socioeconomic material stocks (Fischer-Kowalski, 1997).

Insights from social metabolism regarding socioeconomic material stocks suggest the need to rethink the ‘shallowness’ of material stocks as places to intervene in complex socioeconomic systems as in social metabolism they are defining the system structure and thereby its design. Leverage points research often conflates Meadows’ system dynamic understandings of stocks with the distinct notion of socioeconomic material stocks as represented in social metabolism thinking. This can lead to the latter to be arbitrarily prescribed as a shallow ‘parameter’ (leverage points 10 and 11, Fig. 1) leverage points for system change (Abson et al., 2017). In the following we identify crucial roles of socioeconomic material stocks that make them an essential factor for transformative change.

Socioeconomic materials stocks are directly related to environmental pressures (Duro et al., 2024; Fanning et al., 2020; Haas et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2023; Pauliuk and Müller, 2014). Annual growth rates of the extraction of materials from the environment are at an average annual rate of about 3 % since 2000 (Krausmann et al., 2018). A large proportion of that resource use – ranging from cement and metal production, fossil fuel combustion, to agriculture, forestry, and other land use change — is used for the maintenance and growth of socioeconomic material stocks (including maintaining the stock of humans). Structures of material stocks directly influence current and future resource use in two ways: building up and maintaining material stocks requires enormous amounts of resources. In addition, meeting human needs requires the provision of essential services such as housing, food, transport, communication and many others (Brand-Correa and Steinberger, 2017; Rao et al., 2019). These services in turn necessitate specific

² In fact, also the human population and livestock of a given socioeconomic system are considered part of the totality of stocks in socio-metabolic research. However, these types of stocks are not within the scope of this manuscript but we are focusing on socioeconomic stocks only (built environment and artefacts).

combinations of stocks and flows (Haberl et al., 2017; Kalt et al., 2019; Pauliuk and Hertwich, 2015; Pauliuk and Müller, 2014; Weisz et al., 2015). A decent living space requires, for example, next to the building itself, heating, lighting, and infrastructures for water and energy supply, as well as sewage and waste removal. Likewise, transport requires next to rails, roads or vehicles, energy to power vehicles and regular maintenance or replacement (Carmona et al., 2021). All of this requires continuous resource supply.

Overall, in 2015, two thirds of all materials extracted globally (58 Gt/yr) were associated with socioeconomic material stocks (Fig. 2) such as buildings, infrastructure and machinery, either for their construction and maintenance (43 Gt/yr) or energy carriers for their operation (15 Gt/yr) and the provision of services (Krausmann et al., 2020; Krausmann et al., 2018). About 17 % were throughputs resulting from manufacturing processes like extractive wastes and manufacturing losses or from manufactured products like packaging material and short-lived consumer products (e.g., hygiene products). The remainder of another about 20 % is food and feed which can only be provided because stocks such as tractors, roads, harbours, or halls provide essential services in land cultivation, transport, storage and processing.

Attempts to steer societal transformations towards more sustainable societies often focus on sub-systems or sectors like buildings, transport or industry and tend to treat each of them as if it exists independently and is subject to unique interests, levers and drivers of change (Boas et al., 2016). This makes some sense, politically, but, as Cass et al. (2018, p. 166) put it, “analysis of how infrastructures intersect and influence each other points to the need for systemic forms of intervention that directly address these co-constitutive processes.”

Therefore, while it may be true what Meadows noted, namely that it is time consuming to change the physical stock-and-flow structure, the findings of socio-metabolic research show how crucial growing socioeconomic material stocks are for growing extraction, waste and emissions of resources (Krausmann et al., 2017b). This highlights their leverage potential, and, given time required to change such physical stocks, the importance of making early interventions into such structures.

Socioeconomic material stocks can guide individual behaviour in a sustainable or unsustainable direction (Haberl et al., 2021). Socio-

metabolic approaches argue, that once in place, socioeconomic material stocks develop *momentum* of their own with path dependencies determining future resource use patterns, and, therefore, become an underlying cause of unsustainable levels of resource use. The following examples illustrate this: Two cities might be connected via a motorway with high capacities but lacking high quality rail connections. People, who frequently have to commute, gain more and more knowledge on car use between the cities, where to park the car, etc. and lose knowledge on using public transport. Car use becomes a necessity for commuters. They might demand commuter allowances; company cars might become a norm and people develop habits integrated in their lifestyles for their preferred mode of transport. Freight transport also fully adjusts to the situation and acquires a vehicle fleet apt for road transport between the city pair. Construction companies develop routines and purchase appropriate machinery for maintaining the motorway and it becomes an important source of income for them. Vested interests can lead to lobbying activities at least to keep the transport connection as is. Such a motorway is significantly more carbon intensive than a high performing rail connection. However, GHG savings depend as well on another infrastructure, the electricity generation. If the power is green, GHG savings are significantly higher (Lin et al., 2021; Shen et al., 2023). Housing could be another example with similar benefits: If people live in well-insulated houses that are designed to make good use of daylight, they need very little energy to live at home, even with a higher level of comfort than in poorly insulated houses with high energy consumption.

The present design of these structures lock societies into resource-intensive practices and lifestyles (Cass et al., 2018; Swilling, 2011). The legacy effects of already built structures are considerable (Cui et al., 2019). The GHG emissions from fossil fuels expected for the period 2010–2060, which are required only for the continued utilization of already existing infrastructures until the end of their service life, amount to around 500 Gt CO₂ (i.e. 136 GtC) (Davis et al., 2010; Raupach et al., 2014). Another study found that phasing out existing high fossil fuel infrastructure (e.g. fossil fuel power plants, industrial infrastructure, cars with internal combustion engines) in line with their planned lifespan and replacing them with carbon-free alternatives would still result in emissions totalling 715 Gt CO₂ (i.e. 195 GtC) (Smith et al., 2019). This contrasts with the revised IPCC budget for a 50 % chance of limiting

Fig. 2. The global economy as socioeconomic system with flows that are related in one or the other way to the socioeconomic material stocks (1), which amounted to 961 Gt in 2015. Flows for stock building (2) are needed for expansion and maintenance of socioeconomic material stocks. Throughput materials (3) are extracted and manufactured with stocks like machinery and using infrastructure. Energy carriers (4) also require stocks to be converted into services such as mobility or heat. Food and feed (5) are harvested, transported and in most cases processed as well as distributed by use of stocks. Food and feed are also consumed directly by humans and livestock (6). Overall, extraction and output like emission and solid and liquid wastes are key factors in exceeding planetary boundaries (Source: adopted from Krausmann et al., 2018, 2020).

global warming to 1.5 °C, which amounts to 580 Gt of CO₂ emissions from 1 January 2018 (i.e. 158 GtC) (IPCC, 2018).

A more complex area that is nevertheless worthy of consideration: different socioeconomic systems' structures can be designed entirely differently, meaning they are endowed with fundamentally different social material stocks. In one case, it could be a walking and cycling friendly compact settlement with good public transport and areas of mixed use for living, recreation, shopping, health services, education and working. In another case it could be a sprawled and road centred settlement with specialised areas other than living in some distance. In turn, these different endowments of socioeconomic material stocks do not just create path dependencies as described above, but they also shape the perception of challenges and consequently responses to them (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz, 1999). Just consider that if mobility costs per kilometre of car use rise due to the high resource use (material, energy, land), people living in a compact mixed-use settlement may easily increase active mobility, while people in a sprawled area may call for subsidies due to a lack of alternatives. Thus, socioeconomic material stocks play a role in determining which leverage points are envisioned and prioritised by society.

Based on the above, we put forward two arguments: (1) Socioeconomic material stocks are more than 'parameters' and are entrenched in wider system characteristics. Thus, they are crucial for delays in system feedback and even for the goals to which the system is aligned. Further, to a large extent they define the system's design. (2) Therefore, it is crucial that those using the leverage points framework need to be aware of the difference between stocks as conceptualized in system dynamics and social metabolism and hence, consider the systemic role that socioeconomic material stocks play in transformative change.

3. Understanding the interconnectedness of socioeconomic material stocks with the 'deep' leverage points

What different versions of the leverage points framework have in common is that stocks are classified as shallow, ineffective leverage points. About her decision to rank 'the structure of material stocks and flows' as shallow, Meadows wrote that, "[p]hysical structure is crucial in a system, but rarely a leverage point, because changing it is rarely quick or simple. The leverage point is in proper design in the first place" (Donella H. Meadows, 1999a, p. 10). However, while resource-saving design of planned material stocks is certainly crucial, it is even more critical – as we argue – to also intervene into already existing stocks. For example, the emissions associated with using the currently existing socioeconomic material stocks until the end of their lifetime would greatly exceed planetary boundaries (Smith et al., 2019; Tong et al., 2019). If remaining in place as they are, they will have a long-lasting impact on the future demand of resources (Section 2). The sheer existence of physical structures like road and airplane networks establish social conditions that make it very hard to change course: they depend on sectors selling specific products (e.g., cars) or imply an organization of work and production processes in a manner that assumes existence of that network. This eventually leads to emergence of institutional structures, e.g. laws/regulations of what is 'reasonable'.

If, for example, one has the choice of losing unemployment benefits or accepting a job involving a daily commute by car of one hour in each direction, the presence of a motorway becomes a criterion in the legal provisions. Employers will push for an efficient, publicly financed road infrastructure or commuter allowances to shape the employment market according to their interests.

Meadows often refers to stocks as stabilizing buffers, but socioeconomic material stocks shape the resource flows that a society requires to fulfil demanded services. Whereas leverage points twelve and eleven are mostly concerned with stocks in nature, leverage points ten is most directly related to socioeconomic material stocks. Meadows here mentions specifically road systems, car fleets, plumbing structures, and the general physical arrangement of stocks and flows. However, according

to Meadows (1999a, p.10) those entities "rarely [represent] a leverage point". Leverage point nine, concerned with the lengths of delays, is also related to socioeconomic material stocks as the built environment acts as strong and persistent stumbling block for change initiated at any other point of a socioeconomic system. Still, according to Meadows, all leverage points concerned with the physical structure of a system, i.e., leverage points twelve to nine (as indicated in Fig. 1), are very limited in their effectiveness of initiating system-wide change. Only when describing leverage point eight, Meadows (1999a, p.9) asserted that: "Now we're beginning to move from the physical part of the system to the information and control parts, where more leverage can be found."

Meadows specifically argued that the physical structure "is rarely a leverage point, because changing it is rarely quick or simple" (Meadows, 1999a, p. 9). This description of Meadows on stocks and generally all physical parts of a system as shallow leverage points is debateable for a number of reasons:

- (1) While proper design of stocks is indeed the first choice, changing existing (often deficient) stocks is needed as they have profound and long-lasting effects which hinder or foster change for decades into the future. Therefore, it is not an option *not* to intervene in already existing stocks.
- (2) No leverage point can achieve substantial system change if stocks were to remain unaltered, because subsequent material and energy flows and their environmental impacts could hardly be reduced.
- (3) Neglecting entities that are crucial for system behaviour but not simple to change would also apply to those leverage points classified as 'deepest'.

These three arguments challenge the hierarchy implied in the leverage points framework (i.e., intent shapes design, design shapes feedbacks, feedbacks shape parameters), as the proposed hierarchy neglects how the material world shapes feedback, design, and intent characteristics of a given system of interest.

4. Reconceptualizing the role of stocks for system change

Meadows and other scholars like Mandl (2023), both system dynamic modellers, conceptualize stocks mostly around their level and stabilizing function for systems. According to the proposed hierarchy of leverage points, efforts to change system behaviour and system-wide sustainability outcomes as well as initiating a sustainability transformation by directly intervening into the physical properties of a system are considered ineffective interventions constrained by deeper system properties (Mandl, 2023). This perspective, we argue, ignores the biophysical basis of societies.

We here argue that a leverage points perspective concerned with change of socioeconomic systems has to better integrate and reflect upon the momentum that socioeconomic stocks develop for system behaviour. One of the most important requirements for effectively intervening into a system is an appropriate understanding of the system's dynamics and underlying structure leading to those dynamics. In socioeconomic systems, as discussed in Section 2, socioeconomic material stocks play a crucial role: Firstly, they are key for the reproduction of society and the inflows of resources as well as outflows of wastes and emissions, and hence for its sustainability or transgression of planetary boundaries. Secondly, stocks are key co-determinants of services that can be provided to society like transport or shelter. Thirdly, many different aspects, from the social acceptance of change to worldviews and accepted intentions shape perceptions and provide the background for the acceptance of the various leverage points.

The following example illustrates the interwovenness of the three roles: Copenhagen's cycling history, highlighted by Cass et al. (2018), showcases the evolution of urban transportation infrastructure and societal dynamics. Commencing in the late 19th century, cyclists'

assertion for the edge of the road, initially designated for horse riders, led to the establishment of the Bicycle Path Association in 1897, signalling a departure from elitist transportation modes like horses, then trams and cars. By 1906, bicycles outnumbered horses by 200:1, reshaping institutional perceptions of road usage. Copenhagen's socio-economic context, marked by relative poverty and sustained cycling prevalence through the Great Depression, cycling remained 'too big to fail'. Cycling's symbiotic relationship with residential, occupational, and leisure geographies cemented its political and infrastructural significance, even as automobiles gained prominence. Despite a slowdown in cycling infrastructure development, earlier structures facilitated radial urban expansion, leaving a lasting mark on Copenhagen's landscape, underscoring the intricate interplay between transportation practices, cycle-paths, environmental pressures, urban development, and societal norms until today.

From the leverage points hierarchy and its depiction, one might conclude that stocks are merely a buffer and do not change system structure, but at the same time material stocks *themselves* are part of what determines the system structure. Socioeconomic material stocks are not just a neutral pool that absorbs and balances, they are more than buffers, as the Copenhagen case clearly shows. Socioeconomic material stocks are a key element of the system's structure. When envisaged as socioeconomic systems, societies are permeated by physical infrastructures; they essentially form a society's fabric. They channel environmental impacts through in- and outflows, use, and maintenance, the provision of services (Plank et al., 2021), and the structuring of social and economic activity. They determine what is possible in the individual as well as in the system-wide context almost effortlessly, and what requires huge efforts, and thus guide further development and influence societal norms. Their qualities, functions, and spatial structures are what make them a key entity in the socioeconomic system enabling and prohibiting change. Hence, even though the leverage points hierarchy suggests changing system intent as a priority, this cannot be disconnected from changes in the physical structures of material and energy flows.

In turn, intervening into stocks directly and only to initiate system change, without considering other leverage points, would certainly not be effective. For example, if we only seek to change the socioeconomic material stocks associated with primary energy generation to renewable energy, without also addressing our system goals or the growth paradigm that underpins them (Leverage points 3–1), we are likely to simply run into new environmental limits (Creutzig et al., 2024). To paraphrase Paul Ehrlich, you can bulldoze as much wetland with a solar powered bulldozer as with one running on fossil fuel (Ehrlich, 2023). However, leverage points in sum need to address stocks and how we use them, otherwise the system cannot become more sustainable, irrespective of where the first intervention takes place. Indeed, the crucial question may not be how 'deep' or 'shallow' a particular point of intervention is, but rather how to best coordinate multiple interventions across space and time at different 'systemic depths'. Deeper leverage points might restrict the potential of shallow leverage points, but at the same time, existing stocks do not change automatically once deeper leverage points are triggered. They represent another hard-to-overcome stumbling block if not addressed and incorporated properly. That is why any intervention strategy aiming to change system behaviour needs to reflect upon the inhibiting or enabling role of stocks and, therefore, needs to direct the desired change of stocks. Thus, for a transformation, stocks need to be addressed systematically and purposefully. Caution must be exercised that the growth dynamics of stocks is halted and that, in case of existing stocks, the lifetime savings of the operation outweigh the additional environmental impacts of reconstruction.

While we are not arguing for an adaptation of Meadows' hierarchically structured leverage points scale, we point towards the potential of expanding the concept of stocks as essential for understanding how a socioeconomic system functions, for how system structure is perceived and how system-wide change can be initiated. For these reasons, we

suggest a reconceptualization of the relation of leverage points and stocks, one that embraces stocks as a structuring element of socioeconomic systems. Consequently, stocks cannot be conceptualized from a pure system dynamics perspective and thus only be related to parameters. Rather, they are a critical foundation for the deeper leverage points around feedback, design and intent of a system and therefore require systematic and consistent consideration.

Therefore, like already stressed in several articles on leverage points (Dentoni et al., 2017; Fischer and Riechers, 2019; Linnér and Wibeck, 2021; Patterson et al., 2017; Riechers et al., 2022), no single leverage point whether shallow or deep, will alone change complex socioeconomic systems. We therefore argue that expanding the leverage points by the stock concept and adding it as a cross-cutting dimension can support this. Within a specific infrastructure, incoming and incumbent systems compete and interact (e.g., mobility: active modes, public transport and car mobility). But infrastructures are not isolated, different infrastructures interact as well (e.g. transport networks, settlements, electricity grids, charging stations) (Cass et al., 2018). All this directly affects resource use, waste and emissions, but also influences which practices are convenient, and which are burdensome. Thus, multiple leverage points that simultaneously target different places in these interconnections are needed for a transformation.

As argued above, socioeconomic material stocks are tightly interwoven with other leverage points from a system dynamics perspective. Reconceptualizing stocks reveals how closely they are linked with other leverage points in multiple ways. Adopting a biophysical perspective on socioeconomic systems helps to identify such interconnections between multiple leverage points and stocks. In Fig. 1, we highlighted the leverage points that are perceived as being strongly related to material stocks and flows according to Meadows' original contribution. However, while it is obvious how material stocks and flows are present in the **parameter** system characteristic, they also play an important role for feedbacks, design, and intent of the system (Fig. 3).

While socioeconomic material stocks can cause huge delays, they also influence how fast a certain measure pertaining to infrastructure can be implemented and how fast effects will be visible (leverage point nine). Further, they can act as a self-correcting as well as a self-reinforcing **feedback** loop in a system (leverage points eight and seven). For example, stocks can strengthen or weaken self-correcting (negative) feedback loops when they impede or even almost completely prohibit active mobility. That will be the case when the mobility infrastructure is designed to favour car traffic, which makes it impossible, dangerous, unhealthy, or too time-demanding to be mobile in other ways. Car-dependent infrastructures even trigger fierce resistance to any efforts to change them, as many actors depend in multiple ways on the existing system (Mattioli et al., 2020). In that sense, stocks can be part of feedback loops that exert a self-correcting ability, like preventive infrastructure which punishes those who would like to live or travel differently. On the other hand, stocks can also act as a self-reinforcing (positive) feedback loop. Some infrastructure invites to create more of its own, like roads will lead to more traffic and congestion, which calls in the mind of most urban and landscape planners for more roads which in turn invites even more car use (Knoflacher, 2009). Moreover, roads are an integral element of urban sprawl, which has again a self-reinforcing trend by requiring more cars and more roads.

Acknowledging that material stocks provide system structure goes hand in hand with accepting that stocks also provide **design** characteristics for socioeconomic systems. For example, as the biophysical system structure, material stocks are closely interlinked with the flows of information and rules of the system (leverage points six and five). Smart mobility management with incentives and regulations can prioritize active mobility, public transport and car sharing over individual car ownership and use and consequently reduce the demand for trips, vehicles and even sealed surfaces like roads and parking lots. Likewise, distances can also be subjectively perceived as short as soon as the existing transport infrastructure allows easy access to services and thus

Material stocks in the perspective, as developed by Meadows 1999 and Abson et al. 2017.

Fig. 3. Same representation of leverage points and stocks as in Fig. 1, but with extended connections to and from socioeconomic material stocks. Applying a socio-ecological resource focus on leverage points, stocks are much wider entrenched in the scale: In addition to the direct connections of leverage points to stocks as suggested by Meadows (red direct arrows), arrows in blue from leverage points eight, seven, and four indicate direct relations of leverage points to socioeconomic material stocks (where stocks can act as a lever) when a societal resource perspective is taken up. The bidirectional dotted blue arrows directed between stocks and leverage points six, five, three, and two indicate indirect linkage where socioeconomic material stocks affect how interventions via those leverage points can be envisioned. The desired goal following interventions via leverage points is indicated at the bottom as a system with comparatively lower levels of socioeconomic material stocks, in- and outflows. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

increases social acceptance of active mobility modes (Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020). In turn, sprawled settlements focused on motorized individual traffic offer very limited potential for smart information flows or changes in the rule of the system without reconstructing the biophysical structures. Which type of mobility is possible and which is not, is most often not decided by individuals, but the ones responsible for provisioning of service infrastructures. Who has the power to decide upon new or, more importantly, existing infrastructure? New rules can directly interfere with stocks transformation or limitation.

For the **intent** level of systems, Meadows hypothesized that paradigms, mindsets, and system goals twists “everything further down the list [...] to conform to that goal” (Meadows, 1999a, p. 16). Looking at the biophysical structures underlying current socioeconomic systems, this might not be true. At least not when it comes to the biophysical structures of society. Seemingly disruptive interventions at deep leverage points might be completely halted by physical structures in place, simply because those structures might not conform automatically, quickly, and easily to new system goals, paradigms, or mindset. Infrastructure will impede new goals if they do not conform with the design of existing physical structures. For example, if the goal changes to be net-zero GHG emissions (which conforms to system-wide goals described by Meadows such as long-term survival and resilience) but the mobility infrastructure is laid out for covering short and long distances with motorized vehicles and planes, then the leverage point of the goal

of the system will reach its limits if stocks are not properly addressed. Put differently, if an intervention strategy for system change does not also directly affect stocks, then the impact is limited. This is something we are experiencing right now.

That is why we argue, material stocks need to be targeted better sooner than later. Ideally, via multiple leverage points in a well-coordinated intervention strategy.

5. Conclusions

The leverage point concept is embedded in system dynamics and considers stocks as elements of the system defined by specific characteristics that can determine the state and behaviour of the system. From this perspective, stocks provide inertia and memory to systems, create disequilibrium dynamics and thus act as buffers with a stabilizing effect on flows. However, the leverage point framework does not provide an inherent understanding of which stock elements are present in a given system or how these elements interact. In contrast, a social metabolism perspective can provide a theoretical and empirical basis for understanding the ways in which socioeconomic material stocks shape the emergent behaviour of socioeconomic systems. From this perspective, socioeconomic material stocks are physical stocks of capital which are continuously reproduced and utilized by society.

Contemporary leverage points research often conflates Meadows’

system dynamics understanding of stocks with the distinct notion of socioeconomic material stocks as represented in social metabolism thinking. This can lead to the latter to be arbitrarily prescribed as a shallow ‘parameter’ leverage points irrelevant for system change. The insights from socio-metabolic research on socioeconomic material stocks suggest a need to reconsider the ‘shallowness’ of material stocks as sites for intervention in complex socioeconomic systems. We identify three crucial roles of socioeconomic material stocks that make them an essential factor for transformative change. (1) Socioeconomic material stocks are directly related to environmental pressures, (2) they steer individuals’ behaviour into sustainable or unsustainable directions, and (3) the different endowments of socioeconomic stocks not only create path dependencies (lock-ins) but also shape perceptions of challenges and consequently initiate responses that shape the intent of the system (i.e., deep leverage), which can reinforce unsustainability.

While Meadows acknowledges that physical structures in a system are critical, she states that they are rarely a leverage point because their change is hardly quick or easy. We debate this because (1) everything that is crucial in a system is difficult to change, (2) there is no system-wide change without stock change, (3) stocks are already created and need to be changed, and (4) the long-lasting effects of stocks need to be addressed sooner rather than later. These four arguments challenge the hierarchy implicit in the leverage points framework, as the proposed hierarchy diminishes the way in which the material world shapes the feedback, design and intention of a particular system of interest.

A leverage point perspective that deals with transformative change of socioeconomic systems must, therefore, integrate and reflect the inherent dynamics that socioeconomic material stocks develop for system behaviour much better than has been observed to date. No single leverage point, whether conceptualized as shallow or deep, can alone change complex socioeconomic systems. Expanding the stock concept and adding it as a cross-cutting dimension to the leverage point framework can foster the understanding of the relationships between different leverage points. The new conceptualisation of stocks shows how closely they are linked to other leverage points in a variety of ways. Hence, adopting a biophysical perspective on socioeconomic systems helps to recognise the interconnectedness between multiple leverage points and stocks in a multidimensional and cross-cutting way.

Data statement

Data shown in Fig. 2 are provided in the SI of Krausmann et al. (2018) which can be accessed via the following link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2018.07.003>

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Willi Haas: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **David James Abson:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Helmut Haberl:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Nathalie Spittler:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Dominik Wiedenhofer:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Christian Dorninger:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Data availability

Data Link is provided in at the end of the manuscript.

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